

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D2.1 – Cloud implementation of exemplary workflows

WP2 – Tools Collaboratory: Deployment of life-science data integration and analysis workflows in EOSC

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Executive Summary

The LS RIs rely on a large and diverse set of software tools and workflows that are segregated in different environments and generally not easily reusable across RIs or communities and in most cases not cloud-ready. The core purpose of WP2 is to make these tools findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable in the cloud so that users across the LS RIs as well as the broad scientific community can take full advantage of the European Open Science Cloud. In this context, this deliverable demonstrates the use of technologies identified in milestone M2.1 by applying them to use cases put forward by the RIs.

Project Objectives

This deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

- a. Making tools and workflows interoperable and reusable in the EOSC across RIs.
- b. Building LS RIs connections to the EOSC.

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

Background

WP2 is concerned with running computational tools and workflows in the EOSC. A workflow describes a set of computational tasks and their relationships. A tool is a piece of software used by researchers to carry out a computational task. In WP2, workflows are specified in terms of tools and manage the flow of data between the tools.

LS RIs produce a large and diverse array of tools and workflows for managing, integrating and analysing a variety of data types but as datasets grow larger and more complex, the computational resources required to process and analyse them frequently outgrow resources locally available to scientists. Providing access to both data and compute resources using cloud technologies puts large-scale computation within the reach of all researchers regardless of their location and facilitates sharing and remote collaborations. However, cloud deployment of tools and workflows is very heterogeneous across LS RIs communities. In addition, an increasing number of studies involve workflows relying on methods and tools from domains of the life sciences covered by different RIs (e.g. single-cell studies combining imaging and omics approaches are now common), whose reusability and interoperability is often limited by differences in implementation and segregation into different environments. This motivates the development of a common computational environment that will foster interoperability and tighter integration of data aspects across LS RIs.

Exemplary workflows on the WP2 EOSC-Life roadmap

To address data access, tools interoperability and cloud portability, WP2 focuses on the part of the software stack required to implement workflows, namely tool packaging, containerisation, workflow management systems and other relevant platforms such as computational notebooks. Earlier in the project, WP2 identified a range of relevant technologies already in use in some LS RIs communities (see milestone M2.1). These technologies include the Conda package manager for tool packaging, Singularity and Docker for containerisation, CWL for describing data analysis workflows, Nextflow and Snakemake for running workflows on the command line and the Galaxy platform as a web-based UI for building and running data analysis workflows. In addition, Workflow-RO-Crate, a lightweight approach to packaging workflow components with their metadata based on schema.org annotations in JSON-LD, has been developed and adopted by EOSC-Life WP2 WorkflowHub team in partnership with CWL, GalaxyEurope, Snakemake, Nextflow and specialised WfMS's from the WP3 demonstrators (e.g SCIPION).

These technologies form the basis of the WP2 roadmap towards building an integrated EOSC environment for the life sciences. Exemplary workflows from the LS RIs have then been implemented following this roadmap. The demonstrators in WP3 have also been encouraged to adopt the same approaches, whenever suitable.

Research Infrastructure(s) involved		D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8
		ELIXIR	INSTRUCT	ELIXIR	EMBRC	EuBI	EuBI + ELIXIR	EATRIS	EMPHASIS
Status of the demonstrator	Have the tool/workflows been successfully deployed in the cloud?	yes	yes	yes	no	no	yes	no	no
	Packaging	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Packaging	Bioconda	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Singularity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Docker	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Other (write the name)								
Workflows	Galaxy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	nextflow	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Snakemake	<input type="checkbox"/>							
	Other (write the name)		Scipion	CWL	In progress	XNAT		CWL	
Registries	bio.tools	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	BioContainers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Workflow Hub	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other (write the name)		EBI EMPIAR, RO-Crate	GitHub, DockerHub	In planning	In planning			
WP2 Infrastructure	Galaxy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Kubernetes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>						
	GA4GH	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	OpenStack	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Amazon Web Services	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other (write the name)			Embassy Cloud, de.NBI Cloud	In planning				
Testing	OpenEBench	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>					
	Galaxy WF-testing	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other (write the name)			Travis CI, Zabbix (Monitoring)	In planning			In planning	

Table 1: Status of each Science Demonstrator and the technologies used.

An overview of the technical implementations of the demonstrators is provided in Table 1. In practice, 4 out of 8 demonstrators (D1, D2, D3 and D6) have been successfully deployed in the cloud. These demonstrators all relied on Docker or Bioconda, or both. D1 and D3 also adopted Singularity. All other demonstrators adopted during their development at least one of these three solutions. In terms of workflow managers, the scenario is more diverse, with Galaxy being the most common one (used by 4 demonstrators), followed by Nextflow. Two demonstrators

adopted different solutions: Scipion for D2 and XNAT for D5, because of legacy and field-specific reasons. In terms of computational infrastructure, OpenStack was chosen by 5 demonstrators. Due to the use of sensitive data, D7 adopted the GA4GH framework. The most commonly used workflow repository was WorkflowHub (6 out of 8, corresponding to all the demonstrators that used a public repository for their workflows). Finally, testing technologies were implemented only by three demonstrators, each with a different solution. Overall, the technologies previously identified in Milestone 2.1 displayed a quite high degree of uptake by the demonstrators. Testing technologies were not implemented by 5 out of 8 demonstrators, suggesting that this is not yet a common practice; however, it is also likely that as implementation of the demonstrators has focused on getting them up and running, testing has been left for later stages of the projects.

In addition to the 8 demonstrators selected by WP3 at the start of the project, WP2 also worked on several other projects put forward by the RIs (listed in Table 2).

	Interactive environments (notebooks, remote desktops ...)	Virtual desktop for interactive image analysis	COVID-19 workflows	Big data management software generators	microbiology workflows and tools	Metadata repository (MDR) for clinical studies data objects	AI-based analysis of biobank image data	IMPC data analysis workflows	NMR screening of protein ligands based on NMRpipe	A predictor of protein secondary structure
Research Infrastructure(s) involved	ELIXIR	EuBI	ELIXIR	EMPHASIS / EPPN2020	MIRRI	ECRIN	BBMRI	INFRAFRONTIER	INSTRUCT	INSTRUCT
Short description of the workflow	Interactive environments for exploratory data analysis, data cleaning and data visualisation.	A desktop environment with software for interactive image analysis in the cloud.	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Afu3RG-BOGT5ohQUM20hnGtePZohv-IKQYzx8I-vo/preview#	For a set of data model definitions (the schemas) two interfaces are automatically generated. A graphical browser based single page application to present the user with a standard point and click experience, and	design of CWL workflows : 1 on metagenomics, 1 on genome assembly, CWL genomics tool integration : mothur package, spades, unicycler, bantage, published on github	Designed and developed by ECRIN using Anaconda (Python 3), Django (v. 3.0), Angular (v.9)	Deep learning for tumor recognition on digital pathology images	Enable user driven IMPC data analysis and machine learning application in the cloud	An automated workflow for the analysis of experimental data from NMR-based ligand screening	Machine learning for prediction of protein secondary structure
URL of the service / repository	https://live.usegalaxy.eu	https://vd-portal.embl.de	Workflows: https://covid19.galaxyproject.org WorkflowHub	https://sciencesdb.github.io/	https://workflowhub.eu/	cmdr.org		https://workflowhub.eu/	https://github.com/vincentallier/secondary-structure-prediction	
Status	Have the tools/workflows been successfully deployed in the cloud? yes	yes	yes							
Packaging	Bioconda <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Singularity <input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Docker <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Other (write the name)									
Workflows	Galaxy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	nextflow <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Snakemake <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other (write the name)				CWL		Jupyter	Jupyter	CWL	Jupyter
Registries	bio.tools <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	BioContainers <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Workflow Hub <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Other (write the name)									In progress
WP7 Infrastructure	Galaxy <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Kubernetes <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	GA4GH <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	OpenStack <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Amazon web services <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other (write the name)		Distributed compute & GPU							EGI cloud
Testing	OpenEBench <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Galaxy WF-testing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other (write the name)	Training	Training							

Table 2: Status of RIs projects and the technologies used.

These projects are at different stages of implementation with some of them preparatory work for use cases:

- The big data management software generator aims at facilitating access to data resources by automating the generation of GUIs and APIs. It is now being used towards completion of demonstrator D8.
- A portal application to access a metadata repository for clinical studies data objects.

- Over 20 workflows related to the COVID-19 pandemic have been deployed in Galaxy from tools built with conda and containers and made available in WorkflowHub¹. These workflows address SARS-CoV-2 genome assembly and analysis, evolutionary analysis of viral genomes, proteomics, direct RNA sequencing and cheminformatics screening for millions of compounds that could inhibit the SARS-CoV-2 protease. Of note, analyses are regularly updated by running the workflows again as new data becomes available.
- Several metagenomics, genomics and data integration workflows for microbiology have been or are being implemented.
- An automated workflow for the analysis of experimental data from NMR-based ligand screening has been implemented by natively coding it with CWL, using a tool for spectra processing commonly adopted in the community.
- The virtual desktop project addresses the use of interactive tools with a desktop-bound GUI as is typically the case for image analysis software. It runs a container-based virtual desktop environment in the cloud giving access to the GUI of software also running in containers. An early version can be accessed at vd-portal (EMBL)² which provisions image analysis software.
- The computational notebook projects address the growing interest in using Jupyter notebooks for interactive data analysis. As the initial test case, a machine learning approach to the prediction of secondary structure elements in proteins was taken. This proof-of-concept application can be run on the EGI cloud services using EGI's Notebook environment³. The application itself is available at github⁴. In another application, a deep learning workflow based on Jupyter notebooks has been containerized using Singularity and deployed on an OpenStack cloud infrastructure. The workflow trains neural networks to analyse digital pathology images and identify probable tumor tissue areas.
- In parallel, the European Galaxy server is offering access to Notebooks and virtual desktops as part of the usegalaxy⁵ project. Those interactive tools provide synchronous access to European cloud resources and can be combined with asynchronous workflow scheduling. In addition, a user has full access to data stored inside Galaxy, combining the best of both worlds. An example is given by the Metagenomics community⁶.

Conclusions

The EOSC-Life demonstrators of WP3, as well as a variety of exemplary workflows implemented by the partner RIs, demonstrate the effective uptake of the technologies that WP2 had identified in milestone M2.1 and prioritized during the first year of the project. It also demonstrates that these technologies can form the basis of a cloud environment in which tools and workflows are interoperable across RIs and communities.

¹ <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows?filter%5Btag%5D=covid-19>

² <https://vd-portal.embl.de>

³ <https://notebooks.egi.eu/hub/login>

⁴ https://github.com/vinclaveglia/secondary_structure_prediction

⁵ <https://live.usegalaxy.eu>

⁶ <https://galaxyproject.eu/posts/2020/04/14/integrative-meta-omics>

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
LS	Biomedical Sciences
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GUI	Graphical User Interface
RI	Research Infrastructure
UI	User Interface
WP	Work Package

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is delayed:

No

Adjustments

Adjustments made:

None

